

Rural development and sustainability promotion

Rural depopulation together with the abandonment of traditional agriculture may bring important effects on the territory and to those who inhabit it: weakening of economic and social structures, decrease in human well-being and loss of local identity and social capital. Key strategies to stop rural abandonment is to promote repopulation and support the return of those who live in cities and want to live in rural areas.

A total of **23 activities were identified**, motivated by collective community action and driven by social responsibility, in which four interest groups of the local population participated in different ways (*Neo rural, Local, People who does not live there but has a connection, and Other link*).

Almócita is a pioneer in Europe with the creation of an Intelligent Energy Community.

Almócita as an example of rural innovation

In the last 60 years, the Alpujarra de Almería has experienced a very pronounced depopulation and emigration to urban areas. The main causes are limited economic activity, lack of work and the low value of existing sectors, such as agriculture.

However, in Almócita this trend is reversing. It is a proactive municipality, in which its inhabitants and the local government work cooperatively to promote projects and activities aimed at sustainable development (both ecological and social), with the aim of attracting and establishing population. The local governance of the municipality is playing a key role with new proposals, investment in culture and establishing a close relationship with its inhabitants.

Looking for a good quality of life

Most people have a close relationship with the town, living there or going there regularly. In addition, they feel very linked to the natural environment of Almócita, whether they are local or identified themselves as neo-rural.

Highlighting the activities is key to getting residents to connect with the territory and have a sense of belonging

Not all groups participated in the same way: the activities were mainly led by neo-rural people and people with some connection to the town.

HOW ACTIVITIES PROMOTE HUMAN WELL-BEING IN ALMÓCITA?

Improving good quality of life in Almócita

They strengthen local trade and production of fresh foods, which preserves the landscape and fosters a connection with nature.

They facilitate the flow of knowledge and strengthen the sense of a small community.

Participation in the activities generates tranquility, increases relationships among neighbors, and promotes the local economy.

Some activities preserve traditions and, therefore, protect cultural heritage.

